

**ORAL AND PERIODONTAL HEALTH IN ONCOLOGY
PATIENTS: A CLINICAL AND LABORATORY STUDY****Gulmirakhon Iminjonova**

Andijan State Medical Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19448362>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 01st April 2026Accepted: 04th April 2026Online: 06th April 2026**KEYWORDS**

To perform a comprehensive assessment of dental and periodontal health in oncology patients based on clinical and laboratory indicators, as well as to substantiate the necessity for preventive dental interventions in this patient population

ABSTRACT

The study included 103 patients aged 22–75 years with verified malignant neoplasms (solid tumors and hematological malignancies). All participants underwent a detailed стоматологическое обследование prior to initiation of chemotherapy. The evaluation comprised assessment of dental caries intensity, periodontal pocket depth, bleeding on probing, and oral hygiene status. Laboratory investigations included measurement of C-reactive protein (CRP) levels and complete blood count analysis. Statistical processing was conducted using Student's t-test and chi-square test, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

To perform a comprehensive assessment of dental and periodontal health in oncology patients based on clinical and laboratory indicators, as well as to substantiate the necessity for preventive dental interventions in this patient population.

Methods: The study included 103 patients aged 22–75 years with verified malignant neoplasms (solid tumors and hematological malignancies). All participants underwent a detailed стоматологическое обследование prior to initiation of chemotherapy. The evaluation comprised assessment of dental caries intensity, periodontal pocket depth, bleeding on probing, and oral hygiene status. Laboratory investigations included measurement of C-reactive protein (CRP) levels and complete blood count analysis. Statistical processing was conducted using Student's t-test and chi-square test, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

Results: Dental caries activity was detected in 80% of patients, with a mean DMFT index of 15.3 ± 5.2 . Periodontal pathology was identified in 80% of cases, with severe forms observed in 30% of patients. Patients with severe periodontitis demonstrated significantly elevated CRP levels (12.4 ± 4.1 mg/L) compared to individuals without periodontal involvement (4.8 ± 3.0 mg/L; $p < 0.01$). A moderate positive correlation was established between CRP concentration and periodontal parameters ($r = 0.35$; $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: Patients with oncological diseases are characterized by a high prevalence of dental and periodontal disorders, particularly caries and periodontitis, which may contribute to enhanced systemic inflammatory burden and increased risk of complications during antitumor therapy. Integration of comprehensive dental assessment and санация полости рта into standard oncological care protocols is recommended